

REVISITING WIGNERS MIND-BODY PROBLEM: SOME COMMENTS ON POSSIBLE MODELS OF CONNECTIONS BETWEEN INFORMATION, MIND, AND PHYSICS

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Abstract

From the announcement of this Convention we have learned that 2019 J.B. Rhine address will be delivered by quantum physicists and philosopher Antoine Suarez, who, after meeting John Bell at CERN in 1988 got involved into quantum philosophy. Suarez, as it is said, advocates the philosophical view that all interpretations of quantum physics are basically equivalent.

I will argue that understanding John Bell's real concerns, and following his advice is important if we want to make serious steps toward understanding the coupling between mind and matter as it was first addressed by Eugene P. Wigner, who was one the first great physicists who speculated that the message that quantum mechanics may be sending us is that consciousness may be the most essential part of the ultimate reality. Wigner envisaged that quantum mechanics needs to be replaced by an enhanced theory, whose equations of motion are nonlinear.

John Bell came to a similar conclusion albeit starting from different premises. He argued that quantum theory needs to be enhanced to accommodate real time events (which he related to what he called

"beables" - things that really "are"). What is needed is explicit description, within the mathematical formalism of quantum theory, of the flow of information. I will argue that this can be done. I will argue that in order to understand and to describe, using equations and algorithms, consciousness and psi phenomena, in particular of poltergeist type, further steps are necessary that involve hyperdimensional physics and Kaluza-Klein type theories but developed for low energy phenomena and information exchanges, which is not how contemporary theoretical and mathematical physics is being developed.

1 Introduction

From the announcement of this Convention we have learned that 2019 J.B. Rhine address will be delivered by quantum physicists and philosopher Antoine Suarez, who, after meeting John Bell at CERN in 1988 got involved into quantum philosophy. Suarez, as it is said, advocates the philosophical view that all interpretations of quantum physics are basically equivalent and amount to state that not all what matters for the physical phenomena is contained in space-time.

More precisely, Suarez proposes a novel All-Possible-Worlds interpretation that unifies Copenhagen and Many-Worlds interpretations, and "accounts for divine omniscience without abolishing human free-will" [27].

I am rather skeptical about the usefulness of yet another interpretation of quantum mechanics. In fact I will argue that John Bell himself was desperately trying to convey to us a completely different message, namely that it is not just interpretation of quantum theory that matters, but that quantum theory itself needs a serious cure, that it is crippled and incomplete.

I will argue that understanding John Bell's real concerns, and following his advice is important if we want to make serious steps towards understanding the coupling between mind and matter as it was first addressed by Eugene P. Wigner, who was one the first great physicists who speculated that the message that quantum mechanics may be sending us is that consciousness may be the most essential part of the ultimate reality. Wigner envisaged that quantum mechanics needs to be replaced by an enhanced theory, whose equations of motion are nonlinear.

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modate for real time events (which he related to what he called "beables" - things that really "are"). What is needed is explicit description, within the mathematical formalism of quantum theory, of the flow of information. I will argue that this can be done. I will argue that in order to understand and to describe, using equations and algorithms, consciousness and psi phenomena, in particular of poltergeist type, further steps are necessary that involve hyperdimensional physics and Kaluza-Klein type theories but developed for low energy phenomena and information exchanges, which is not how contemporary theoretical and mathematical physics is being developed.

2 John Bell - Against the measurement

My first visit to CERN was in 1982. John Bell had just published his paper "On the impossible pilot wave" [3] which triggered his interest in "hidden variable" theories and so called "impossibility proofs". The abstract of his paper reads:

The strange story of the von Neumann impossibility proof is recalled, and the even stranger story of later impossibility proofs, and how the impossible was done by de Broglie and Bohm. Morals are drawn.

And the main moral he gives us is:

A final moral concerns terminology. Why did such serious people take so seriously axioms which now seem so arbitrary? I suspect that they were misled by the pernicious misuse of the word "measurement" in contemporary theory. This word very strongly suggests the ascertaining of some preexisting property of some thing, any instrument involved playing a purely passive role. Quantum experiments are just not like that, as we learned especially from Bohr.

Bell was evidently angry at those physicists who paid unjustifiable attention to "impossibility proofs", and he was also angry at those who generously used the term "measurement" in quantum theory, without really understanding what that term meant and what they were doing. It is a very important issue and I will discuss it below. But first about John Bell and CERN.

At that time, 1982, I was already interested in the foundations of quantum theory. When I came to CERN I visited John Bell in his office trying to learn from him what it is that he considers most important. I do not remember today all the details of this discussion, but I think John Bell was already worrying about the fundamental conflict between quantum theory and relativity. His 1984 paper “Speakable and unspeakable in quantum theory”, ends with the sad realization that “... we have an apparent incompatibility, at the deepest level, between the two fundamental pillars of contemporary theory...”

In those years, at CERN, foundations of quantum theory were not on the main agenda. In 1981 a seminal paper by a Princeton physicist Edward Witten appeared, “Search for a realistic Kaluza-Klein theory”, a paper inspired by the 1938 paper by Einstein and Bergmann - trying to take extra dimensions, those beyond our space and time, seriously: ”... we ascribe physical reality to the fifth dimension ...”. At CERN I followed this line of thought, that today provides another necessary step for taking into account the phenomena of mind (cf. [7, 8]. In 1983, together with R. Coquereaux, we published the first results of our collaboration at CERN, ‘ ‘Geometry of Multidimensional Universes” [9]. This collaboration continued during my second and third stay at CERN, and we have developed new methods of tapping into hyperspatial geometries resulting in several papers (cf. eg. [10]) and the monograph “Fiber Bundles, Kaluza-Klein Theories And All That ...” [11]. After that excursion into hyperspatial dimensions I returned to the foundations of quantum theory and started seriously studying the message coming from John Bell.

Unfortunately John Bell left us in 1990. A year before his premature death he published his last angry message to the community of quantum physicists, the paper entitled *Against “Measurement”*. What John Bell was pointing at was that quantum theory, in its present state, is seriously deficient; and it is deficient not because we do not have a correct interpretation; it is deficient because it is using concepts that do not have adequate representation in its mathematical formalism, such as the concept of “measurement” or “observation”. Bell’s abstract points to the necessity of some new dynamics:

It is argued that the word ”measurement” be banned in serious discussion of quantum mechanics. Expositions of quantum ”measurement” theory by Landau and Lifshitz, by Gottfried, and by van Kampen, are analysed. When more precision is required,

ideas like those of de Broglie and Bohm, or those of Ghirardi, Rimini, and Weber, seem inevitable.

Then he goes on:

Surely, after 62 years, we should have an exact formulation of some serious part of quantum mechanics? By "exact" I do not of course mean "exactly true". I mean only that the theory should be fully formulated in mathematical terms, with nothing left to the discretion of the theoretical physicist..

But quantum mechanics, in its present form, does not have in its mathematical formalism a place for "observation" or "measurement". These are just words that do not have a counterpart in the mathematical formalism. So, in particular, John Bell suggested to ban the word "measurement", to replace it with the more objective sounding "experiment". At the same time he opted for enhancements of quantum theory that describe real, objective, events that happen in time, and have their own dynamics. He mentioned explicitly de Broglie-Bohm pilot wave mechanics, where quantum particles may have their own objective trajectories, and also Ghirardi-Rimini-Weber (GRW) formalism, where the quantum wave function experiences repeated "quantum collapse" events, though for unclear reasons.

While de Broglie-Bohm mechanics keeps the dynamics of the quantum wave function unchanged, the GRW formalism adds random and irreversible quantum jumps that happen in real time, even though not in our world of tables and chairs, but rather in the abstract Hilbert space; but at least something happens without the need of any human intervention. We are closer to the description of the real world, though still far away from the world of tables and chairs.

In his "Quantum mechanism for cosmologists" John Bell also made some comments about Everett "many world interpretation", which, by the way does not provide any dynamics whatsoever for objective events. Bell comments there that

Everett's replacement of the past by memories is a radical solipsism extending to the temporal dimension the replacement of everything outside my head by my impressions, of ordinary solipsism or positivism. Solipsism cannot be refuted. But if such a theory were taken seriously it would hardly be possible to take anything else seriously.

3 Quantum Future and the Birth of Event Enhanced Quantum Theory (EEQT)

3.1 Schrödingers Cat

Erwin Schrödinger, one of the founders of quantum theory, introduced his thought experiment, that involves the poor animal, in his 1935 paper “*The present situation in quantum mechanics*”¹ According to the orthodox interpretation of quantum mechanics, a cat locked in a chamber with a radioactive material that can trigger a killing poison would be in neither alive nor dead state until someone “looks” inside, in order to check. This “neither alive nor dead state” is, according to the orthodox quantum theory, a “superposition” of “cat alive” and “cat dead” states. After presenting this strange situation Schrödinger focuses on *knowledge*, that is on “what do I know”, instead of focusing on what “objectively happens”. That is how he got himself into a “paradox”, and his paradox has been examined again and again in hundreds if not thousands of papers and books by physicists and by philosophers ever since. A typical conclusion is that reached by John Gribbin in his book “*In Search of Schrödingers Cat*” [14]: “there is no underlying reality to the world.” Wigner [13, p. 284] came to a similar conclusion though contemplating less cruel experiments involving his friend rather than cat.

3.2 Quantum Future and the Birth of Event Enhanced Quantum Theory (EEQT)

During all those years, while working on hyperdimensional geometries of space and time, and hidden dimensions that extend outside of space and time, I could not stop thinking about that poor cat. So I came back to my interests in the foundations of quantum theory in 1990. My original idea was one that could be a good subject for a sci-fi book: to construct a detector and the amplifier of our “free will”. I was sure that if some enhancements were added to the standard quantum theory, we would be able to measure fluctuations of our free will (caused perhaps by some distant cosmic phenomena). I also decided to solve the problem posed by John Bell: there should be a way

¹English translation of Schrödinger’s paper was originally published in Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society, 124, 323-38, and then appeared as Section I.11 of Part I in Ref. [29].

to enhance quantum theory by adding to it what was missing - the exact mathematical description of the dynamics of “experiments”, when electrons tracks are caught on a photographic plate, chairs fall and table crash, all in real time. I also thought that perhaps we can use our consciousness in order to change quantum probabilities. Moreover, as I was thinking, we should be able to simulate our experiments, together with their results, the “events”, on our computers. I proposed my ideas to Philippe Blanchard of the University of Bielefeld, and we began the “Quantum Future” project.

The work on the theory developed by Philippe Blanchard and myself, started in June of 1990.

My initial idea was, as I wrote then in my personal diary at that time: to unify matter fields with information fields, to understand the role of time, the role of the wave function. I wrote to Philippe Blanchard at the University of Bielefeld, and he accepted my proposal. I went to Bielefeld a year later and that was the beginning of our collaboration.

In September 1991, impressed by Ilya Prigogine’s ideas [2], I realized that the key to the realistic description of Nature is the philosophy of “open systems”, the *acceptance of indeterminism and irreversibility at the fundamental level*, and also the acceptance of the empirical fact, stressed repeatedly by Niels Bohr, that *not all is quantum*. A year later we sent our first paper “On interaction between classical and quantum systems” for publication in Physics Letters [5]. At first it was only a description of the dynamics of statistical states, but soon we were able to uncover the real time description of events in individual quantum systems coupled irreversibly to classical ones. We gave our theory the name *Event Enhanced Quantum Theory*, in short “EEQT”. The main developments and the results were summarized in 1995, in the paper *Event-Enhanced Quantum Theory and Piecewise Deterministic Dynamics* [6]².

The main concept of EEQT is the concept of “events”. Events are “real”, they are usually objectively “recorded” and they happen in real time, that also can be recorded. All our data about the external world consists of recorded, objective events. The formalism of the standard quantum mechanics has no place for these events, and is unable to simulate their appearance using the mathematical apparatus of Hilbert spaces and Schroödinger’s equation.

²At that time Joop Houtkooper visited us in Bielefeld, and we discussed possible links between our approach and his Ganzfeld experiments and “observational theory” of psi phenomena [20], but we did not find immediate common paths.

3.2.1 Bohmian mechanics

De Broglie and Bohm added classical trajectories to the quantum wave function, where the wave function guides the classical particles in a multidimensional configuration space of the system, but this theory, called nowadays *Bohmian mechanics* has epistemological defects. First of all, as has been noticed by Wigner in his paper on “Physics and the Explanation of Life” [28] “we do not know any case in which the influence is entirely one-sided.” Wigner was talking there about matter and consciousness: “Since matter clearly influences the content of our consciousness, it is natural to assume that the opposite influence also exists, thus demanding a modification of the presently accepted laws of nature which disregard this influence” But the same objection applies to the guiding wave function of the Bohmian mechanics. The quantum wave function guides classical particles, acts on them with a strange “quantum potentia”, but there is no back action. The classical part of the wholeness has no influence on the quantum part, which is rather suspicious and suggests the need for a modification that would describe also the *back action*. There is also another objection to Bohmian mechanics that is sometimes called “causal mechanics” and considered as such.³ But that is not the case. Bohmian trajectories, in order to agree with statistical observations, have to start with random initial data, and the randomness, for unexplained reasons, has to be governed by Born’s probabilistic formula. Calling this “an equilibrium condition” [12] only tries to sweep and hide this problem under the carpet.

3.2.2 Ghirardi, Rimini, and Weber

EEQT has been conceived, under the influence of the thoughts expressed by John Bell, as a logical extension of the theories developed in the years 1970-1990 known under the names “spontaneous localization”, “dynamical reduction” and, finally, “GRW”, or the “Ghirardi–Rimini–Weber” model. The need for seeking such extensions of the standard quantum theory was clearly stated by John Bell in his paper “Are there quantum jumps?” [4] This is what John Bell wrote about Schrödinger (emphasis mine):

³For instance in his paper “Facts, Values and Quanta” Appleby writes: “In short, it seems to me that Einstein, given his conceptual standpoint, had every reason to reject dice-playing God. If one chooses to follow the Einsteinian road then one had better look for a fully causal interpretation of quantum mechanics such as the de Broglie-Bohm interpretation.”

At an early stage, he had tried to replace ‘particles’ by wavepackets (Schrödinger, 1926). But wavepackets diffuse. And the paper of 1952 ends, rather lamely, with the admission that Schrödinger does not see how, for the present, *to account for particle tracks in track chambers ... nor, more generally, for the definiteness, the particularity, of the world of experience*, as compared with the indefiniteness, the waviness, of the wavefunction. It is the problem that he had (Schrödinger, 1935a) with his cat. He thought that she could not be both dead and alive. But the wavefunction showed no such commitment, superposing the possibilities. *Either the wavefunction, as given by the Schrodinger equation, is not everything, or it is not right.*

GRW theory was built on the second assumption: that the wave function given by the Schrödinger equation is not right. In EEQT, on the other hand, it is clearly realized from the very beginning that the wave function given by the Schrödinger equation *is neither everything nor right*. John Bell continues then (emphasis mine):

Of these two possibilities, that the wavefunction is not everything, or not right, the first is developed especially in the de Broglie-Bohm ‘pilot wave’ picture. Absurdly, such theories are known as ‘hidden variable’ theories. Absurdly, for there it is not in the wavefunction that one finds an image of the visible world, and the results of experiments, but in the complementary ‘hidden’(!) variables. Of course the extra variables are not confined to the visible ‘macroscopic’ scale. For no sharp definition of such a scale could be made. The ‘microscopic’ aspect of the complementary variable is indeed hidden from us. But *to admit things not visible to the gross creatures that we are is, in my opinion, to show a decent humility, and not just a lamentable addiction to metaphysics*. In any case, the most hidden of all variables, in the pilot wave picture, is the wavefunction, which manifests itself to us only by its influence on the complementary variables. If, with Schrodinger, we reject extra variables, then we must allow that his equation is not always right. I do not know that he contemplated this conclusion, but it seems to me inescapable.

Indeed, not only in the pilot wave picture, but in the whole quantum theory as it is being taught, the wave function itself is “the hidden variable”. It lives in

a world that is not ours, in some infinite dimensional Hilbert space, or in some abstract “space of quantum states” or “complex probability amplitudes”.

Ghirardi, Rimini and Weber (as well as almost all other physicists working in this direction) did not pay any attention to this fact. Later on Roderich Tumulka understood that something is rotten in the Kingdom of Dynamical Reduction Models and proposed, what he has called “the flash ontology”. Yet he stopped half-way admitting that there must be something that is “real” - he called it “flashes”, but he did not dare to come to the logical conclusion that these “flashes” are nothing else but “events”, changes of the state of some classical system, that can have their causes, their own dynamics, dynamics that can be formulated in the everyday language of “classical physics” and, this way, bring new insights into the whole structure of theoretical physics and its relation to the world as we perceive it and try to describe it.

In fact GRW, with its “spontaneous localization” is a particular crippled case of EEQT. What is hidden within the old GRW. or the newer “flash” ontology, is made clear and explicit in EEQT.

3.2.3 EEQT - Dynamics and Binamics

EEQT is a dualistic (and even syncretistic) theory. It contains the old quantum dynamics, governed by the Hamiltonian operator H that encodes well know forces and interactions, but it contain also what is called *binamics* – in contrast to the part associated to H , which is called *dynamics*.

As I have pointed out above Schrödinger confessed that the standard quantum mechanics is unable to account for particle tracks. Fig. 1 shows one such track. Anderson received Nobel Prize in 1932 for identifying this track with the trace left by the positron - antimatter particle. The positron here is supposed to be rather fast - it has the speed of about 0.99 of the speed of light. Nevertheless the track is certainly made by activating grains of the photographic emulsion one by one. The next dot is always made in the direction of the previous dots, giving the impression of continuity; as if there was a real particle there. But we know from quantum theory, specifically from Heisenberg’s uncertainty relations, that it is impossible for a particle to have a smooth trajectory. It is our mind that interpolates between dots and tells us that these dots must have a common cause. But what is this cause? And how exactly are decisions being made to create the dot at that and not at some other time, and at that and not some other place? Quantum theory is unable to answer these questions Neither can Bohmian mechanics

Figure 1: Positron track. By Carl D. Anderson.

nor GRW, nor All-Possible-Worlds. Placing the dots is certainly a random process, and certainly it is somehow triggered by placing the matter, the grains of emulsion, on the path. But random according to which algorithm? And on the path of what? On the path of some wave function? Where is this wave function coming from? Where does it live? What does it eat, or who/what eats it?

EEQT answers these questions, and it can simulate the creation of particle tracks in time, dot after dot [16].

While dynamics deals with the laws of exchange of forces, binamics deals with the laws of exchange of bits (of information). These two sets of laws refer to different projections of one reality and neither one of these projections can be completely reduced to another one. ‘Moreover, bits’ are as real as ‘forces’ - except that they are concerned with the world of information rather than the

world of matter. There is a wavy, quantum part of the world Q , governed by quantum Hamiltonian dynamics and quantum non-Boolean logic, and there is the classical part of hard data C that may have its own dynamics and that is governed by the classical two-valued logic. The two worlds are connected by a new kind of two-way interaction, the binamics described by the coupling typical to open systems and encoded in a family of operators V

We, the conscious beings, are partly Q and partly C (and partly of something else). But not only we are subjects and spectators - sometimes we are also actors. We can manipulate *states*, we can not manipulate dynamics, but binamics is open. It is through V and C that we can feedback the processed information and knowledge. We may have partial freedom of intervening, through C and V , at bifurcation points, when die tossing takes place.

It then became possible to formulate a relativistic version of the theory, though only by adding to the four dimensions of space and time the fifth dimension, the organizing dimension known among the physicists as “Fock-Schwinger time” [17]. Quantum theory moves us from our three space and one time dimensions to some infinite dimensional space where wave functions live and possibly jump. But what exactly is the substratum of all that activity? And where does the information live?

4 Gravity and Hyperdimensional Reality

How to explain macroscopic poltergeist phenomena [23, 26], where matter moves through matter, chairs move through walls, tricksters [15] play with our reality? The only possible road is through hyperdimensional physics, which research I have suspended during my “Quantum Future” years. To address these questions I had to return to the universal phenomenon of gravity and its hyperdimensional extensions. But how to reconcile quantum mechanics with gravity? Einstein looked into this problem long ago, but hopes with Kaluza and Klein theories have been long ago put in the grave. Attempts to construct some kind of “quantum gravity” or “theory of everything” did not bring expected results. Moreover all these attempts by theoretical physicists were addressing high energy phenomena, of no importance whatsoever for understanding the relation between mind and matter.

The possible relation of extra dimensions to psi phenomena has been an active arena for research for a long time. One of the first scientists who started looking into possible connections was Elisabeth Rauscher. In 2009 she

published a monograph “The Holographic Anthropic Universe: Formalizing the Complex Geometry of Reality”, coauthored with Richard L. Amoroso [1]. Unfortunately one should not take this text seriously. For instance these authors write [1, p.]

We have examined the modification of gauge conditions using higher symmetry groups such as SU_2 , SU_n and other groups such as the $SL(2, c)$ double cover group of the rotational group $SO(3, 1)$ related to Shipovs Ricci curvature tensor [12,13] and a possible neo-aether picture.

The point is that Shipov, who is the Russian physicist that invented the concept of “torsion fields”, often thought to be responsible for psi phenomena in Russia, wrote his “Theory of Physical Vacuum” with so many serious mathematical errors that his “theory” looks like a joke [19]. When Amoroso and Rauscher quote Shipov, it can only mean that they are probably joking too.

Another approach to extra dimensions became quite popular in recent years. Our 3D space is being considered as a moving thin “brane” in a higher dimensional “bulk”. The known interactions propagate only within our space, while gravity reaches beyond into hidden dimensions. So far the research is mainly intended to deal with high energy phenomena and gravity [22]. But the idea may become increasingly important when put together with the Einstein’s old dream of constructing a Unified Field Theory. Mendel Sachs published two monographs [24, 25] containing his ideas and research results in this direction. He stresses the fact that quantum theory is incomplete, and cannot be made complete as long as it is a linear theory. Eugene Wigner came to the same conclusion when discussing the Mind-Body problem [13]. But Sachs makes the next step, when he notes that General Relativity is a nonlinear theory, and when he tries to derive Quantum Mechanics from General Relativity. I am skeptical about the logic of Sachs’ reasoning, but I can see hope in pursuing this direction, especially when adding geometries of hidden dimensions. This may be related to the problem of Free Will. Quantum randomness may seem to be necessary to account for the Free Will choosing this or other sequence of events among those potentially possible. But we still have the problem of describing mathematically both the freedom experienced and the actions chosen. As Wigner has been stressing in his “Remarks on the Mind-Body Question” [13] *nonlinearity is necessary*:

It was pointed out already by Bohm (...) that, if the system is sufficiently complicated, it may be in practice impossible to ascertain a difference between certain mixtures, and some pure states (states which can be described by a wave function). In order to exhibit the difference, one would have to subject the system (friend plus object) to very complicated observations which cannot be carried out in practice. This is in contrast to the case in which the flash or the absence of a flash is registered by an atom, the state of which I can obtain precisely by much simpler observations. This way out of the difficulty amounts to the postulate that the equations of motion of quantum mechanics cease to be linear, in fact that they are grossly non-linear if conscious beings enter the picture.⁴

Bohmian mechanics and GRW are linear theories when it comes to the dynamics of quantum waves. EEQT, that extends Bohmian mechanics by adding explicit classical degrees of freedom [18], is nonlinear, but it is not a complete theory because the coupling to gravity is still missing. Therefore some kind of multidimensional Unified Field Theory is needed, nonlinear, nonlocal, and acausal - from our human perspective, and yet elegant and simple from the perspective of some different kind of intelligence. What we call the Laws of Nature may apply only to our dimensions. Other dimensions may have different laws of nature, less restrictive, giving more freedom in non-material dimensions. Quantum theory will then emerge as an effective theory that simply could not be understood at all, it only can be stolen and utilized. But there will be another theory merging material and non-material, with algorithms replacing differential equations, algorithms simple and yet leading to incredible complexity of live phenomena.

5 Conclusions

We want to know how Nature does what it does? Of course the question is very difficult to answer even in a classical theory. Maxwell equations tell us how the electromagnetic field in the vacuum propagates. We can solve these

⁴The non-linearity is of a different nature from that postulated by W. Heisenberg in his theory of elementary particles [cf., e.g., H. P. Durr, W. Heisenberg, H. Mitter, S. Schlieder, K. Yamazaki, Z. Naturforsch., 14, 441 (1954)]. In our case the equations giving the time variation of the state vector (wave function) are postulated to be non-linear.

equations in a finite volume, for a finite time, and with a finite precision using our supercomputers. But how is Nature herself doing it, apparently effortlessly? What resources is Nature using? Some hidden powers not visible to us? The question "how Nature does what it does" become even more striking when it comes to simulating quantum theory that includes continuous monitoring and quantum jumps. To simulate one quantum jump nonlocal calculations are needed, including integrals over the whole space and time. Even simulation of a simple particle track with a dozen dots involves hours of computer time. For Nature it is almost instant, and no visible resources are being used. How? Evidently something is going on outside of space and time. But where and how exactly?

Of course one possible answer is that we do not have to *understand* all these mysteries of Nature. Perhaps, paraphrasing Wigner [28], "our intellectual capabilities may have their limits just as the capabilities of other animals have". Therefore it is enough for us to be able to steal secrets from Nature, and to be able to utilize them in a meaningful way. After all Prometheus did not have to know the physics and the chemistry of fire! He had to know how to cheat the gods - that's all.

And yet, and that is the way of science, we should try to understand better and better how Nature does what it does, and how matter intertwines with mind.

As stated by the Indian physicist C.T.K Chari at the closing statement of the Proceedings of the 1975 Parapsychology Foundation Conference [21]:

Parapsychology, in my view, requires more than a reconstruction of quantum mechanics. It calls for a major "paradigm shift" in our notions of probability and information, especially in biology.

In my view we need to know and we need to understand, as much as humanly possible, what Nature is about, how it does what it does, and why? Where do the laws of Nature come from, what forces Nature to obey these laws, and where does the intelligence and order come from?. I am arguing that it all points toward the hidden dimensions of information and organization, ruled by algebra and geometry that is free from the necessity to obey any one-dimensional causal order.

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